

Banking liquidity behavior in times of crisis in Brazil¹

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Abstract

This study's central objective was to examine the contextualization of the liquidity preference behavior of private banking firms in the Brazilian economy from March 2011 to December 2021. This important period can explain a set of important crises; in particular, the 2014 financial crisis and those that followed until COVID-19. These events damaged the Brazilian development process, especially after Dilma's impeachment, which transferred the Presidency to President Temer. In the subsequent destabilized political environment in Brazil, a new extreme right political orientation emerged, deepening the national economic (especially the financial) crisis. To empirically demonstrate the severe consequences of the conjecture, we applied the structural break test and the Chow method to this period to identify four breakpoints. The results suggest that, in periods of structural breaks, private banks offered higher levels of credit but tended to retract this credit supply during, periods marked by environments of extreme uncertainty due to poor economic performance. This means that in periods of economic recession, banking firms became more rational and thus retained their liquidity.

Keywords: Banks; Liquidity preference; Structural breaks

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1. Introduction

Our study seeks to contextualize private institutions' preference for bank liquidity from March 2011 to December 2021, which is a crucial period to explain the 2014 recession and its consequences in the following years until the COVID-19 crisis. In addition to other internal and external factors, the reduction of economic output (recession) is associated with the mismatch with monetary policy. Accordingly, we propose the hypothesis that in times of crisis, banks in Brazil have a greater preference for liquidity. This study aims to analyze the preference for bank liquidity from a post-Keynesian view. For this, we employ a structural break method to identify disruptive periods of bank credit rationalization (Feio (2021)). Furthermore, we have two other special objectives: 1) to present an understanding of the preference for bank liquidity and 2) to analyze and contextualize the preference for the banking liquidity of Brazilian banks.

The economic recession between 2014 and 2016 began with the economic policy decisions implemented by President Dilma Rousseff in 2012, which aimed to boost economic growth through a combination of tax exemptions, nominal exchange rate depreciation, and basic interest rate reductions. This period has been rigorously reviewed by the post-Keynesian literature. Researchers, such as Resende & Bittes Terra (2017) and Sicsú et al. (2021), present their arguments to demonstrate that the central cause of the recession was a large neoliberal agenda imposed in Brazil⁷, especially after August 2016 when President Michael Temer assumed the presidency. This was not the only Brazilian struggle; in 2019, a more rigid neoliberal agenda was proposed by the recently elected President, Jair Bolsonaro, and his designated Minister of Economics, Paulo Guedes.

The central problems related to Dilma's period are connected to the evident ideology conflict between what the President and what the President of the Central Bank (at that time, Alexandre Tombini) and later the Minister of Economics (Joaquim Levy) believed⁸. Both economists' ideas reflected a strong neoliberal agenda, but Dilma was elected with a economic perspective in social areas. The conflict between Dilma and the other two authorities, coupled with the state of the financial system, created an unsustainable political (and economic) environment. Indeed, Suplicy (2017) and Singer (2020) point out the subsequent financial instability that surfaced, leading to a deepening of economic (especially financial) crises. After the impeachment, Dilma's successor, Michel Temer, designed a more rigid and profound neoliberal agenda, but struggled with workers' legal rights and benefiting the financial system more than the social sector. In addition, despite his low popularity, an unknown politician named Jair Bolsonaro started to raise a similar (and sometimes equal) economic agenda, which was continued by his future Minister of Economics, Paulo Guedes.

⁷ The neoliberal agenda did not exclusively happen in Brazil. Mollo et al. (2022) demonstrated the development of the agenda around the world, distinguishing the consequences for uneven and advanced economies.

⁸ See Saad-Filho (2020).

With Bolsonaro's ascension and election, he and his Minister proposed to reduce the government's economic presence to a minimum and to grant the Central Bank autonomy⁹. The second proposal is central to understanding the present financial conjecture, since, in this case, all monetary decisions started to be exclusively under the purview of the Central Bank President. However, their plans were dashed at the beginning of 2020 by the COVID-19 pandemic crisis which, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), caused the global economy to sink into a severe economic recession.

Although Brazilian society represents only 3% of the world's population, the country was responsible for almost 11% of the deaths over the course of the pandemic. The central reason for this awful reality is that the elected President and his ministers did not pay sufficient attention to the WHO guidance. Instead, they focused solely on the growth of the economy while ignoring the population's health and well-being, which is an essential characteristic of the neoliberal agenda (see Navarro (2020)). In this vein, after the tragedy, non-traditional economists (especially post-Keynesians) such as Resende et al. (2021) and Pollit et al. (2021) started to study the economic implications of Bolsonaro's foolish political economy.

Thus, to verify the behavior of the spread of private banking firms in relation to interest in credit operations and the totality of loans and determine how these two latter variables affect the former while considering the economic context that Brazil faced in relation to the preference for bank liquidity from March 2011 to December 2021, we applied the structural break test using the Chow method (Chow (1960)). It is worth mentioning that with regard to the econometric analysis, bank spread was the dependent variable, and interest in credit operations and total loans were the independent variables. In addition, public banks were not included since they did not impact the economy in the same way as private bank. Moreover, as their objectives differ, including them could distort the results.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 elucidates the preference for bank liquidity in the post-Keynesian view, and Section 3 deals with the discussion about Brazilian banks and their preference for liquidity. Section 4 discusses the study methodology, and Section 5 presents an analysis of the results. Section 6 discusses the results. Finally, Section 7 contains the concluding remarks.

2. The preference for bank liquidity in the post-Keynesian view

According to de Paula (2006), when making their asset portfolio allocation decisions, banks are guided by earnings expectations, taking into account the preference for liquidity, which occurs as part of a trade-off between monetary returns and liquidity premium affirms that the theory of liquidity preference demonstrates that agents opt for different degrees of liquidity that are compensated by higher or lower returns. Banks are

⁹ If readers wish to delve deeper into the theme, we recommend reading Schaefer (2018) and Dweck (2021).

firms that carry out financial intermediation, such as transferring resources from agents with surpluses to agents with deficits, promoting and influencing means of payment, financing, and interfering with the level of economic activity, like GDP growth.

Accordingly, banking institutions manage the funds they raise and the portfolios of active investments in order to maximize their profits. At the same time, they seek to preserve their financial position by balancing assets and liabilities. The differential in the rates paid and charged for passive and active operations, respectively, called the spread, considerably influences banks' economic performance. Additionally, the compatibility, in terms of maturity and convertibility, of the assets available in currency, in the face of demands for deposits and withdrawals by creditors, defines, in general terms, the degree and risk of banks' liquidity.

In the classic view, banks act passively, being mere intermediaries in the transfer of resources between savers and investors. However, the post-Keynesian view opposes the classical approach, highlighting banks' capacity to establish financing conditions for the economy and determine the level of economic activity. Minsky and Kaufman (2008) emphasize that the decisive behavior of banks in certain financing conditions influences various agents' level of spending, which, in turn, affects the real variables of the economy, such as output and employment. From another perspective, banks can be perceived as any capitalist firm that makes decisions in an environment of strong uncertainty for the purpose of obtaining greater profits.

These profits fundamentally result from the income of banks' active portfolios, because, according to Minsky and Kaufman (2008), banks' profits are derived from the fees they charge to accept debts, consign funds, and provide other financial services. The first two, described by the author as visible assets of banks, are basically made up of loans (credit operations) and stocks and bonds (investments), with loans represented by funds the bank provides to businesses and individuals in exchange for the promise that they will repay the borrowed monies at a future date. Bonds and stocks, or investments, reflect purchases from the financial markets, and also carry the promise of payments at various future dates.

Thus, the diversification of liquid financial assets made available by banks depends on the formation of their expectations regarding the future profitability provided by the speculative and intermediation market. That is, the level of risk will depend on the trade-off between obtaining greater profitability from a portfolio (asset), restricting access to loans, and providing greater liquidity to the market. Moreover, it hinges on the economic context (Keynes (2016/1936)). Thus, according to the post-Keynesian theory, banks manage their liabilities through both the administration of reserves and the search for new deposits in order to obtain the funds required to finance active portfolios. Keynes (2016/1936) formulated the theory of preference for liquidity, which considers the interest rate a reward for agents with surpluses who sacrifice liquidity. For example, the interest paid as remuneration for bonds rewards those with a

lower degree of liquidity compared to those who opt to hold on to currency.

Davidson (1978) relates the liquidity of an asset to the time of convertibility into currency, the ability to retain value (i.e., transforming an asset into currency without a loss of value), and the existence of a secondary market for resale of the asset. According to L. F. R. d. Paula (1998), who examined banks' financial context and the speculative approach, banks converting assets into currency demand some degree of protection and care given the risks assumed. Moreover, Paula (1998) found that in conditions of uncertainty, banks seek to safeguard their asset portfolios by achieving a trade-off between profitability and the scale of liquidity preference since the profitability of an asset tends to be inversely proportional to the degree of liquidity.

According to this logic, when banks have optimistic expectations they favor profitability over liquidity and are more likely to expand investments with longer terms and risks and embrace credit and liquid investments, thereby reducing their safety margins. In contrast, when expectations are pessimistic, banks tend to prefer to preserve liquidity, reduce the supply of credit, and give greater emphasis to papers such as government bonds. The following section of this article is intended to present the liquidity preferences of Brazilian banks.

3. Banks and their preference for liquidity in Brazil

Regarding the active investments of banks in Brazil, Munhoz and Gaspar (2012) observe that banks in Brazil have always sought greater profitability in times of greater stability and exhibited an increased preference for liquidity in times of instability, particularly noting that soon after the Real Plan, banks expanded credit applications as a way to offset inflationary revenues. However, the authors states in his work that from 1997 onwards, the exchange rate crises in Asia, Russia, and Brazil gave rise to greater investments in more liquid bonds and securities. In the early 2000s, when the environment as more favorable and stable, there was an expansion of credit applications in Brazil, with the credit/GDP ratio more than doubling from 22% in 2002 to approximately 40% in 2008. The American crisis, also known as the subprime crisis, was triggered in mid-2007 due to an increase in real estate values that was not accompanied by an increase in the population's income. This caused a housing bubble in the United States that eventually spread to the rest of the world. The realization of what had caused the crisis in the following years led to new reallocations of private banks' portfolios as they sought greater liquidity, once again reducing investments in credit operations. Despite the cyclical behavior of banks observed here in relation to credit applications and the evolution trend of these applications over time, in Brazil, according to Prates et al. (2009), the banking industry has historically based most of its operations on carrying public debt securities than on granting credit, especially due to high-interest rates.

According to L. F. Paula and Alves Jr. (2002), the problem of banks choosing assets while considering the trade-off between profitability and liquidity has its

particularities for the Brazilian banking market since in this country public debt securities, which represent the most liquid assets, are low risk and profitable, given the high basic interest rate available in the country. de Paula (2006) also highlights this fact, further emphasizing the relationship between the Central Bank and the banking sector in terms of public debt management, which allowed banks to organize their portfolios in such a way that they combined liquidity and profitability, even in difficult circumstances when the credit volume banks was relatively low.

In 2010, with GDP growth, the highest recorded in the previous 20 years, there was an approximate 7.5% increase in credit applications. According to Alencar Junior et al. (2019), this scenario made Brazilian banks follow this expansion movement; that is, with more positive expectations about the future, they started to expand credit, going from approximately 24.6% of GDP in 2003 to about 47% of GDP in 2010. According to Araújo (2012), this intensity of economic growth was corroborated precisely by the fact that private banks expanded the volume of credit operations at rates higher than those of public banks throughout the cycle, thereby sustaining the force of that process.

This growth scenario lasted until the second quarter of 2014. From then on, the macroeconomic indices progressively worsened and Brazil entered a serious economic recession. According to Oreiro (2017), from that period onwards the country began to face a recession, with the most significant and most lasting drop in the level of economic activity since the end of World War II. Safatle, Borges, and Oliveira (2016, p. 30) state that in the period from 1945 to 1980 there was not a single year in which the variation of Brazilian GDP was negative. Recessions were “growth recessions”; that is, periods in which the economy expanded at rates below its historical trend. In the recessive period from 1980 to 1983, Brazilian GDP fell by 6.3% in real terms. According to Alencar Junior et al. (2019), the crisis definitively impacts the supply of credit as it creates an environment of uncertainty in which banks are afraid to grant loans and end up reducing the supply. Thus, it can be said that a financial crisis directly affects the supply of credit.

In this scenario, we still have to take into account the anti-cyclical posture of public banks According to Costa (2014), in the face of the global financial crisis from 2008 onwards, Caixa Econômica Federal, Banco do Brasil, and BNDES (Banco Nacional de Desenvolvimento Econômico e Social) abandoned their preference for liquidity after the federal government reacted to the tightening of credit in the market by using these large federal public banks to irrigate the domestic economy with liquidity and mitigate the recession by granting credit.

From a theoretical perspective, the analyzed articles align with post-Keynesian (PK) ideas, especially regarding the pro-cyclicality of bank behavior and the endogenous theory of money. The pro-cyclicality is clearly described (see Mollo et al, 2022). This dynamic is central to financial instability from the PK viewpoint. Regarding the endogenous theory of money. This reflects the post-Keynesian critique of

financialization and the autonomy of fictitious capital. In the same sense, da Silva Vinhado and Belém (2013) state that in Brazil public banks have a lower preference for liquidity compared to private banks. Many studies like Mazzucado (2014) indicate that public banks fulfil the role of State institutions in terms of offering resources to finance projects that could not have been met by the private sector, possibly due to market failure.

The subprime crisis is central to the analysis, presented as the event that exposed the contradictions of financial globalization. Paula and Ferrari Filho (2009) shows that the crisis originated from the growing default on high-risk mortgage loans in the United States, which were transformed into liquid products through securitization: “A securitização, que serviria para diluir riscos, na prática serviu para esconder riscos - títulos lastreados em hipotecas eram emitidos por instituições financeiras de grande porte, sendo tais ativos classificados como grau de investimento por uma agência de rating” (Paula and Ferrari Filho, 2009, p.2). In Brazil, the development of securitization mechanisms is noted: “No mercado de títulos, desenvolveram-se mecanismos de securitização, estimulados pelo crescimento de investidores institucionais, em que firmas e bancos se financiam ‘empacotando’ rendas a receber” (Paula and Ferrari Filho, 2009, p.2). This shows that, following financial liberalization, Brazilian financial institutions also adopted practices similar to those that contributed to the subprime crisis, increasing the complexity and fragility of the national financial system.

4. Methodology

This study analyzes whether there were structural changes in the data, what these changes were, and the economic contexts that affected the evolution of the banking spread before and after the structural breaks. Thus, a linear regression of the data (bank spread vs. interest on credit operations and total loans) was performed for each period of the structural break. Further, we analyzed the results of descriptive statistics before and after the break and compared the data in order to understand the different economic scenarios that culminated in the breakpoints (years).

To situate the methodological choice, previous applications of the Chow test are briefly noted. Allaro et al. (2011) used the Chow test for 420 observations related to the years 1974–2009, aiming to analyze the following variables from Ethiopia: import, export, and GDP, and found three structural breakpoints for the years 1992, 1993, and 2003. In Luitel and Mahar’s (2015), study, the Chow test was used with 41 samples in the periods 1973–2014 to analyze the US GDP, which revealed only one structural break in 1997. Aronu et al. (2019) used the Chow test with gamma distribution and the standard normal distribution, with 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 observations related to the period 1989–2015. The test was also applied to GDP, which uncovered only one structural break. Feio (2021) employed three different structural break tests: Chow, Bai- Perron, and Cussum, aiming to analyze the debt GDP ratio of Brazil using 203 observations corresponding to the years 2002–2020. The results

indicated five structural breakpoints relating to the years 2005, 2008, 2011, 2014, and 2017. This study was a more complete work than that of Feio, Rossi, and Leal (2022) for the same variables analyzed in the same period. The current study is innovative because it applies the Chow test to 130 observations corresponding to the years 2011–2021 for the following variables in Brazil: bank spread, interest on credit operations, and total loans, revealing four points of structural breakpoints.

The data used in this study were credit indicators, which were available in the Bacen series generator system¹⁰. The data are related to the bank spread, interest on credit operations, and the totality of loans, which are all loans indicated in the Bacen database as total concessions after compiling the credit operations of individuals and legal entities. The 130 observations available for the research were those relating to the months of March 2011 to December 2021 because there is no record in the database for the period prior to March 2011. In operational terms, linear regressions were estimated for subperiods defined by the breakpoints identified by the Chow test, maintaining the same specification across regimes to allow a direct comparison of coefficients. The banking spread was treated as the dependent variable, while the interest rate on credit operations and the total volume of loans were included as explanatory variables.

The exclusive use of the Chow test was adopted to directly and parsimoniously assess coefficient stability at economically motivated and clearly identifiable breakpoints over the study period (e.g., the 2014–2016 recession and the COVID-19 shock), consistent with the post-Keynesian hypothesis of shifts in banking behavior during crises. While alternative methods such as Bai–Perron (endogenous detection of multiple breaks) or recursive stability tests (CUSUM/CUSUMSQ) could be useful in broader exploratory approaches, their concurrent application would increase complexity, the risk of overfitting, and the need for multiple-comparison adjustments, without providing indispensable evidence for the article’s central argument, which requires a focused test on the dates of interest. These alternatives are acknowledged as valid extensions for future work or supplementary material; however, transparency, reproducibility, and adherence to the study’s substantive scope were prioritized here.

1. Test Chow: Some Considerations

According to Chow (1960) it is very common to use simple linear regression to analyze economic relationships; for instance, average consumption in relation to income or the quantity consumed of a given good can be linearly regressed in relation to its price. Furthermore, the quantity consumed can be regressed against the price of complementary goods or substitutes or against revenue, costs, profits, sales, interest rate, liquid assets, and corporate actions. When regressing an economic relationship with two variables (simple regression), it is important to check whether it remains stable over more than one time period and whether this relationship can be applied to two

¹⁰ For more information, please, see <https://acesse.one/yEBNms>

other distinct economic variables; for instance, analyzing the consumption pattern of Brazilians before and after the 1980s. It is worth mentioning that “statistically, these questions can be answered by testing whether two sets of observations can be considered as belonging to the same regression model” (Chow, 1960)). However, two periods or groups of economic variables are not necessarily equal. Although a certain group of companies may be similarly affected with regard to earnings, this may not occur in the same way with regard to liquid assets. According to Chow (1960), “Statistically, we are asking whether the subset of coefficients in two regressions are equal.”

Considering a sample with n observations in a simple linear regression model in which Y is the dependent variable and X is the independent variable and ε is the estimated error (Chow (1960)) we get:

$$Y_1 = X_1\beta_1 + \varepsilon_1 \quad (1)$$

where X represents the number of defined variables, and β_1 is the regression coefficient that indicates the slope of X , which is identical to 1. The ε is an independent variable, which is “normally distributed with a zero mean and a standard deviation of σ ” (Chow (1960)).

Considering the matrix relationship of the various forms that x can take on a set of values, we get: $X_{11}, X_{12}, X_{13}, X_{21}, X_{22}, X_{23}, X_{31}, X_{32}...X_{np}$, where X represents the row number and p is the number of columns. By assuming that $n > p$ is not a singularity of the matrix x , it is possible to estimate the parameters $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4... \beta_n$ and the standard deviation (σ) (Chow (1960)).

According to Chow (1960) both the regression and the prediction interval will have their hypothesis test for the same samples involved considering the number of m observations equal to 1, and the covariance analysis will be $m > p$. The prediction interval for the arithmetic mean of a quantity m of additional observations considered in Equation (1) assumes that Y_1 and ε_1 have a single column of vectors with n elements, and that X_1 has n (rows) and p (columns); and that β_1 has a single column of p vectors (value), the coefficient responsible for the regression angle. By estimating the least squares of β_1 of the first sample, the following equation can be obtained:

$$b_1 = \left(X_1'X_1\right)^{-1} X_1'Y_1 = \beta_1 + \left(X_1'X_1\right)^{-1} X_1'\varepsilon_1 \quad (2)$$

$$Y_2 = X_2 + \varepsilon_1 \quad (3)$$

It is noteworthy that $X_1'X_1$ is the cross-product matrix of p , which are the X_s' of the first sample. In addition, when adding the additional m observed being presented in the model listed below (Chow (1960)):

$$d = Y_2 - X_2\beta_1 = X_2\beta_2 - X_2\beta_1 + \varepsilon_1 - X_2(X_1'X_1)^{-1}X_1'\varepsilon_1 \quad (4)$$

Giving us the mathematical expectation of d :

$$E(d) = X_2\beta_2 + X_2\beta_1 \quad (5)$$

To obtain a statistical result with a null hypothesis in which $\beta_2 = \beta_1 = \beta$, one can consider the expectation $E(d) = 0$ as one makes use of the quadratic equation $d'(Covd) - 1d$.

$$d'(Covd) - 1d = [\beta_2'X_2' - \beta_1'X_2'] [I + X_2'(X_1'X_1)^{-1}X_2']^{-1} [X_2\beta_2 - X_2\beta_1] \left(\frac{1}{\sigma^2}\right) + [\varepsilon_1'\varepsilon_2'] [-X_1'(X_1'X_1)^{-1}X_2'] [I + X_2'(X_1'X_1)^{-1}X_2']^{-1} [-X_2'(X_1'X_1)^{-1}X_1'] \left(\frac{1}{\sigma^2}\right) \quad (6)$$

Still, according to Chow (1960) in the case of the alternative hypothesis $\beta_2 \neq \beta_1$, $d'(Covd) - 1d$ will tend to a non-central X_2 distribution. However, given the null hypothesis, the ratio of the F statistic (which is the variance test or Chow test) considering $n \sim p$; that is, $F(m, n \sim p)$, the test will tend toward a reduction in its interval of prediction when $m = 1$. The result of the F statistic can be seen in the following equation:

$$\frac{d'(Covd)^{-1}d\left(\frac{1}{m}\right)}{\frac{S_1^2(n-p)}{\sigma^2}\left(\frac{1}{n-p}\right)} = \frac{d' [1 + X_2'(X_1'X_1)^{-1}X_2']^{-1} d}{S_1^2 m} \quad (7)$$

The F statistic of Equation (7), the prediction interval, the additional observation, and the analysis of covariance when $m > p$ are applicable in the general linear regression hypothesis test, which can be applied to ascertain whether the totality of the sets of the coefficients of the two regressions is homogeneous. In this way, “the size m of the second sample is considered greater than p and then reduced to 1” (Chow (1960)). Finally, the Chow test or variance test proposes testing the subset of the coefficients in two regressions, which enables us to analyze changes in slope and direction in trends in a time series (Chow (1960)).

Thus, the F test is the variance ratio test that takes into account the residual sum of squares of Equation (1) and Equation (3) plus a third equation whose result will indicate a significance level or of the result. If the results are stable, the significance level will be 1%, 5%, or 10%, indicating that the result is not statistically significant (there is no structural break, which is the null hypothesis). However, results whose values are above the aforementioned percentages indicate that the F statistic is significant. A change in the values of the parameters under analysis indicates there is a structural break; thus, the null hypothesis will be rejected (Luitel & Mahar (2015)).

As the null hypothesis indicates that there is no structural break, rejecting it means that there is a structural break. According to Equation (8), to find the value of the

F statistic, tests of ordinary least squares (OLS) are performed for the entire period OLS_t under analysis, as well as tests of OLS before the break period, OLS_1 , and the period after the breakpoint, OLS_2 . The OLS_t test, which includes the residual value of OLS for the entire period of the time series under analysis, is traditionally performed considering that the regression has stable parametric variables. In the test of OLS_1 , which represents the residual value of OLS before the break date, and the test of OLS_2 , which indicates the residual value after the breakpoint, it is assumed that the regression is performed considering oscillations in the parametric variables (Luitel & Mahar (2015); Aronu et al. (2019)).

$$F = \frac{\frac{OLS_t - OLS_1 + OLS_2}{k}}{\frac{OLS_1 + OLS_2}{n_1} + n_2 - 2k} \quad (8)$$

Thus, still considering Equation (8), k denotes the number of variables being estimated in the model (or the number of parameters); n_1 is the sample size of the first period before the structural break; n_2 is the sample size of the second period (i.e., after the structural breakpoint); and $2k$ is the number of parameters estimated in each model (in this case, two). When the entire period (OLS_t) is stable, there are no statistically relevant changes; however, when the sum of squares of the residuals of different periods is distinct $OLS_1 \neq OLS_2$, it means that the parameters are not stable, which may indicate the presence of a structural break (Luitel & Mahar (2015) and Aronu et al. (2019)).

5. Analysis of results

When analyzing the evolution of the bank spread considering the behavior of the interest of the credit operations and the totality of the loans, the structural breaks were determined using the Chow method. Consequently, we perceived that there were breaks at Points 27, 61, 86, and 69 (see Table 1), which correspond with the months and years of May 2013, March 2016, April 2018, and March 2020.

The four points of the structural breaks (Break periods are indicated by the blue lines in the graphs.) correspond to the three intervals of the evolution of the time series that illustrate the behavior of the bank spread in the period from March 2011 to December 2021 (10 yrs and 10 mos), for which the mean value was 17.42 and the standard deviation was 2.69.

Table 1: Values for Numerical Simulation

Break Points	27	61	86	109
Year (Month)	2013(5)	2016(3)	2018(4)	2020(3)

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

The correlation coefficient derived using Pearson's method indicates a positive correlation of 0.875 of the spread with interest, which means that the increase in the proportion of bank spread varies in proportion to the increase in the interest rate. Conversely, the negative correlation is expressed in the opposite relationship of -0.284 of the spread with all loans, indicating that economic agents become resistant to raising money by borrowing when the market has high interest rates.

The linear model explains 79% of the variance of the dependent variable from the regressors (independent variables) included in the analyzed linear model. The linear model's adjusted coefficient of determination, R^2 , explains 78% of the variance of the dependent variable from its regressors (independent variables) included in the analyzed linear model. The graphical results of the analyzed periods can be seen in Figure 1, which shows a downward trend of less than 14% for the spread in the year 2012 until mid-2014. The spreading curve had recovery peaks and a tendency to increase in 2015 and 2016, reaching a maximum growth point in January 2017 with rates close to 24%.

Figure 1: Behavior of the risk premium, measured by the bank spread (2011–2021)

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

The V-shaped curve starts in February 2012 and ends in mid-2017, indicating a recession period lasting approximately five years. In 2018 and 2019, the spread curve starts to decline, with a brief recovery peak in 2020, and in 2020 and 2022, the rate reached a "valley" of less than 15%. Interest in credit operations explains the behavior from March 2011 to December 2021 (10 yrs and 10 mos), in which the mean value was 24.93 and the standard deviation was 3.78.

The correlation coefficient by Pearson's method indicates a positive correlation of 0.875 between the interest rate and the bank spread; that is, the higher the interest rate, the greater the bank spread. A negative correlation of -0.474 of interest with all loans was also identified, indicating the higher the interest rate, the lower the number of loans offered by banking firms to economic agents in this context.

The graphical results of the analyzed periods can be seen in Figure 2, which shows a downward trend of around 20% for the interest rate in 2013 and an upward recovery in the years 2014, 2015, 2016, finally peaking at 32.54% in January 2017 of

the inverted-V-shaped curve (upside down). After achieving peak growth, the yield curve decreased in the years 2017, 2018, 2019, and 2020 until reaching a "valley" region (minimum point) of 18%. The behavior of the yield curve forms a V until the end of the analyzed period (December 2021), which is the COVID-19 pandemic period.

Figure 2: Behavior of the interest rate of credit operations (2011–2021)

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Total loans are expressed by credit operations released (in millions) by the National Financial System (SFN) and the segments of individuals and companies in the period March 2011 to December 2021 (10 yrs and 10 mos). The average value of these operations was 254,558.73 BRLs (million) and the standard deviation of 52,551.72 BRLs (million), given that loans throughout the period ranged from 192 million to 449 million BRLs. The correlation coefficient derived from Pearson's method indicated a negative correlation both in relation to the bank spread and in relation to the interest rate. The graphical results of the analyzed periods indicated in Figure 3 point to an increasing supply curve in the number of loans offered by banking firms to economic agents.

The loan supply curve has a rising trend with volatile and irregular periods of rise and fall. The loan record in March 2011 was more than 192 million BRLs, peaking at more than 262 million BRLs in December 2013, indicating a loan increase of at least 36%. Despite the fluctuations from January 2014 to December 2017, the average value of loans was just over 230 million BRLs, with a total value of 273 million BRLs lent at the end of that period.

Figure 3: Behavior of total loans: Total loans (2011–2021)

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

As can be seen in Figure 3, from 2018, there was a significant increase in the borrowed amounts in the context of the third structural break (April 2018). The amount borrowed peaked at 302 million BRLs in December 2019. In the year of the fourth and last identified structural break, there was another increase in funds borrowed in February 2020 (288 million BRLs), and in March 2020, this amount reached close to 370 million BRLs. From this last structural breakpoint (March 2020), the average amount borrowed was 336 million BRLs, which increased to an absolute value of 449 million BRLs in December 2021.

6. Discussion of results

The 2013 recession, which spanned the second quarter of 2013 to the fourth quarter of 2016, was the last and biggest economic recession in the history of Brazil. The 2018 the Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (IBGE) survey revealed that 13,800 industries were closed in that period, causing investment in the industrial sector to decrease by approximately a quarter. In addition, a total of 70,900 companies left the market in the years 2015–2016 (IBGE (2013)).

The Economic Cycle Dating Committee (CODACE) collects CODACE data, aiming to establish reference chronologies for Brazilian economic cycles. In their first meetings, monthly and quarterly dates were established for the business cycles that took place from 1980 onwards. Rossi and Mello (2017) compared four periods of major crises in Brazilian history based on the annual income contraction: the Great Depression in the 1930s; the debt crisis in 1980; the confiscation of savings from the Collor government in 1989, and the recent crisis of the Covid-19 Pandemic. And verified that the accumulated GDP drop was not more than 7% in any of these periods, except for the current one, 2015–2016, which was marked by two years of strong GDP reductions. There were recessive episodes throughout the 20th century; however, none had an impact such a large enough to cause a contraction in GDP. The reality changed in the year 2014, when the real GDP showed a simple growth of 0.5%, followed by contractions of 3.5% in the following two years. This context can explain the two structural breaks in May 2013 and March 2016, which were the result of banking firms'

pessimistic expectations in relation to the national economic scenario.

Negative expectations about the future reduce investments, and, as Oreiro (2017) points out, in general, sudden changes in investment spending result from changes in entrepreneurs' expectations regarding the rate of return on capital. According to Keynes, this occurs due to the uncertainty inherent in the investor's decision process, which always involves extreme precariousness with respect to information about the indicators that can affect a rate of return. One common convention is to believe that unless there is a concrete reason to expect a change, the current situation will persist indefinitely.

Oreiro (2017) and Carvalho (2018) claim that the combination of the drop in oil prices in the international market and the Lava Jato Operation were decisive factors of the drop in investment seen in 2014, suggesting that the resulting uncertainties consolidated the reversal expectations associated with the worsening of the political crisis and its repercussions on the Brazilian economy. Thus, from the years 2014–2016, Brazilian banks reacted with excessive prudence, showing their preference for liquidity and causing a portfolio reallocation movement, strong credit retraction, which contributed even more to the deceleration of economic activity.

The question of expectations can be seen in the third structural break in April 2018, when the economy was recovering from rising unemployment rates and increasing informality. Although inflation in the period remained relatively controlled, fuel prices gradually increased, raising the cost of transport. In addition to these elements, the uncertainty of the electoral period weighed heavily on the formation of economic agents' expectations.

The fourth structural break occurred at the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis in March 2020, when social distancing measures were applied, which included the closure of non-essential business activities. Faced with negative expectations owing to the pandemic's global context, the State acted to foster the economy by increasing liquidity. For Keynes (2016/1936), the only way to stimulate private investment, in addition to measures to support consumption through social programs for the unemployed, is through government investment. The economic policy strategies adopted by the government affect its expectations and its state of confidence in the market.

To solve this problem, the State must act as a lender of last resort to mitigate the effects of the pandemic, stimulating animal spirit. To circumvent the negative impacts of the pandemic, companies benefited from programs such as the Emergency Credit Access Program (Paec), the National Support Program for Micro and Small Businesses (Pronampe), new agreements for debt payments, and other financial contributions necessary to promote economic activity. This demonstrates how fiscal policy needs to be aligned with monetary policy to balance investment levels in times of recession and crisis. In an environment of uncertainty, the ex-ante marginal capital efficiency of potential private investments is low, and there is no confidence regarding the uncertain

future.

7. Final thoughts

In addition to Pearson's correlation, Spearman's correlation was also high for the relationship between bank spread and interest rate (84%), confirming the banks' intention to lend at high-interest rates in times of high uncertainty regarding the future behavior of economic agents, as well as investors' intention to invest at more attractive interest rates. Conversely, banking firms become more rational during periods of economic recession and thus retain liquidity. The negative correlation of the spread (Spearman's method) with loans (-0.217) and interest on loans (-0.486) reconfirmed that the larger the loan, the lower the amount of liquidity in the economy during moments of uncertainty.

In all four periods of structural break, banks tended to retract the supply of credit because they had to act in an environment of extreme uncertainty. Moreover, their actions in an environment of economic and political instability generated representative crises. Thus, banking firms redirected their loan capital to more liquid assets due to the negative expectations in the behavior of the banking spread, as shown in Figure 1. The behavior of the banking spread in the analyzed period entered an upward trajectory at various times, indicating a reduction in the preference for bank liquidity as a result of more optimistic expectations from economic agents.

The theories of Keynes and the post-Keynesians that banking firms prefer liquidity was confirmed in the scenario of uncertainty when banks withheld loans that, if made available for investment spending, would have raised the level of employment, with the multiplier effect of employment and income on the economy, thus reducing the costs of maintaining unemployed workers. In other words, as Keynes points out, it is necessary to rescue the basic principles of an anti-cyclical fiscal policy, establishing investment spending, taxation, and State loans as key instruments that guard against involuntary unemployment, which occurs often in times of economic crisis¹¹.

¹¹ See Table 2.

Table 2: Empirical Papers

Paper	Methodology	Sample	Obs	Application	Number and years of structural breaks
Allaro et al. (2011)	Chow test	1974–2004	420	import, export and GDP	3 (1992, 1993, and 2003)
Luitel and Mahar (2015)	Chow test	1973–2014	41	GDP	1 (1997)
Aronu et al. (2019)	Chow test with gamma distribution and the Standard Normal	1989–2015	15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100	GDP	1 (2005)
Feio (2021)	distribution Chow, Bai-Perron and Cussum test	2002–2020	203	GDP ratio debt	5 (2005, 2008, 2011, 2014, and 2017)
Feio, Rossi, and Leal (2022)	Chow test	2002–2020	203	GDP ratio debt	5 (2005, 2008, 2011, 2014, and 2017)
Feio, Dos Santos, Alencar, Oliveira, and Leal (2023)	Chow test	2011–2021	130	bank spread, interest on credit operations and total loans	4 (2013, 2016, 2018, and 2020)

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Other future studies may reveal more about the behavior of bank liquidity by considering the offer of government credit during the pandemic period to identify whether there is a preference for bank liquidity in regions that have adopted the business incentive programs mentioned in this study. Furthermore, it would be interesting to use other structural break tests, such as Bai-Perron and Cussum (Cumulative sum), together with Chow's test to analyze whether there are changes in the results of structural breaks using other methods. Another no less important suggestion is the use of Perron's (1989) unit root tests to test the mean and variance. The regression method, which is generally used, is OLS, which is based on the estimation of variables whose mean and variance are constant over time without seasonality. Depending on the case, it is possible that the mean and variance are not

constant; that is, they can change over time. When this happens it may mean that they are not stationary; that is, the unit root varies in the time series. In this case, the null hypothesis is rejected, so the mean and variance in all the analyzed variables are not constant. With the null hypothesis (that the mean and variance are constant) rejected, it can be concluded that the variables analyzed are not stationary and subsequently inferred that structural breaks were confirmed in all years analyzed in the time series. Therefore, it would be important to use the Dickey-Fuller (DF) or augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test in future studies involving structural breaks to analyze public debt (Allaro et al., (2011))

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APPENDIX

I) Spearman's Correlation

			Spread	Interest Rate	Loans
Kendall tau b	Spread	Coefficient of Correlation	1,000	0,654**	-0,146*
		Sig. (Bilateral)	-	0,000	0,014
		N	130	130	130
Interest Rate		Coefficient of Correlation	0,654**	1,000	-0,334**
		Sig. (Bilateral)	0,000	-	0,000
		N	130	130	130
Loans		Coefficient of Correlation	0,146*	-0,334**	1,000
		Sig. (Bilateral)	0,14	0,000	-
		N	130	130	130
Spearman's ρ	Spread	Coefficient of Correlation	1,000	0,845**	-0,217*
		Sig. (Bilateral)	-	0,000	0,013
		N	130	130	130
Interest Rate		Coefficient of Correlation	0,845**	1,000	-0,486**
		Sig. (Bilateral)	0,000	-	0,000
		N	130	130	130
Loans		Coefficient of Correlation	-0,217*	-0,486**	1,000
		Sig. (Bilateral)	0,13	0,000	-
		N	130	130	130

* The correlation is significant at the 1% level.

** The correlation is significant at the 5% level.

II) Pearson Correlation

			Spread	Interest Rate	Loans
Spread	Coefficient of Correlation		1.000	0.875**	-0.284**
	Sig. (Bilateral)	N	- 130	0.000	0.001
Interest Rate	Coefficient of Correlation		0.875**	130	130
	Sig. (Bilateral)	N	0.000	1.000	-0.474**
Loans	Coefficient of Correlation		130	- 130	0.000
	Sig. (Bilateral)	N	-0.284*	-0.474**	130
			0.001 130	0.000 130	1.000- 130

III) Bivariate Correlation

Data		Spread	Interest Rate	Loans	
Data	Coefficient of Correlation	1	0.080	-0.247**	0.803**
	Sig. (Bilateral)	- 130	0.368	0.005	0.000
	N	0.080	130	130	130
Spread	Coefficient of Correlation	0.368	1.000	0.875**	-0.284**
	Sig. (Bilateral)	130	- 130	0.000	0.001
	N	-0.247**	0.875**	130	130
Interest Rate	Coefficient of Correlation	0.005	0.000	1.000	-0.474**
	Sig. (Bilateral)	130	130	- 130	0.000
	N	0.803**	-0.284* 0.001	-0.474**	130
Loans	Coefficient of Correlation	0.000	130	0.000	1.000
	Sig. (Bilateral)			130	- 130
	N				

IV) Analysis of Variance and Regression Coefficients

Model	Sum of Squares	gl	Average Square	F	Sig.
Regression	740.341	2	370.171	235.298	0.000 ^a
Residue	199.797	127	1.573	-	-
Total	940.138	129	-	-	-

V) Abstract of the Model

Model	R	R2	Adjusted R ²	Standard Error
1	0.887 ^a	0.787	0.784	1.25427

a. Predictors: (Constant), Loans, Interest Rate